

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Triyandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol. XIV, Book. III -IV

JULY - DECEMBER 2022

SRF

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohanam

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohanam@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumarcs@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

dr.rjinu@gmail.com

Contents

The tantric concept in “Vātāpi Gaṇapatiṃ bhaje”-A study	Dr.Pradeep Varma.P.K	7
Śākta Brahmins of Kerala and their rituals with esoteric and exoteric dimensions	Dr. Ajithan. P. I	14
Lanka’s Princess as an Art of Reclaiming Beauty	Dr. M S Gayathri Devi	37
Role of Ayurveda in Geriatric Nutrition	Dr. Gopikrishnan P. T., ,Dr. Haritha Chandran,	
	Dr. Haroon Irshad	51
Manuscriptology: An Overview -	Dr. Keerthi P, Prof. Ramadas P.V. Dr. Haritha Chandran,	
	Dr. Leena P.Nair	58
Spell Checker for Sanskrit Sentences based on Morphological Analysis-	Dr. Namrata Tapaswi	66
Appreciation of Muttusvami Dikshitar’s Navāvaraṇa Kṛti in the Raga Śāṅkarabharanam. -	Mr. Ratheesh P R	77
A Reference Frame for Self-Studies and Self-Regulatory Mechanism of Vedas: Personality Changes - [Swami Parmarth Dev,	Sadvi Dev Priya, Anjali Prabhakar and Paran Gowda]	85
Taxation in Dharmaśāstra -	Dr. Tarak Jana	100
Developmental Stages of <i>Camatkāra</i> in Sanskrit Poetics	Dr. Sudip Chakravortti	114
Elevating the modern educational experience: Correlating ‘Practical Vedanta’ and ‘Bratacārī’ -	Dr Anusrita Mandal	124
Dharma: The Bed Rock of Social Philosophy of Renaissance Thinkers of Kerala. -	Rakesh. K	134
The Concept of Pratibhā and its Implications; Gleanings from Vākyapadīya -	Dr. Sarath P Nath	144
Vaijayantikośa- Nature and Methodology-	Athira.T	153
Analytical study of Śabda -	Dr.N.S.Sharmila	167
Temple architecture: Classification and characteristics	Dr S Radhakrishnan	173
Knowledge of the Heart in Ādi Śāṅkarācārya’s Upaniṣad Commentary	Jyothi. L	181
The Tradition of Nyaya in Kerala -	Niveditha Sathyan	187
Drona: The Practitioner of Injustice -	Dr. G. Reghukumar	195
Karma Yoga Concept in Shrimad Bhagavad Gita: A Conceptual Frame Development - Anjali Prabhakar and Paran Gowda		202
Śrī Jagannāth and Vaiṣṇavism -	Dr.Nilachal Mishra	211
Morals and Teaching of Values for Human Being in Shrimad Bhagavad Gita -	Ramesh Kumar Awasthi	217

Status of Women Depicted in Manusmriti -	Dr. Shylaja S	223
Authoritative Works on Rāja Yoga - A Brief Reflective		
	Sunitha S.	235
Rig Veda and Astronomy -	Girish V.	242
Traces of Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara in the Śaiva Scriptures of Odisha -	Dr. Anil Kumar Acharya	247
तत्त्वशास्त्रे चित्सुखप्रकाशितं स्वप्रकाशत्वमित्यद्वैततत्त्वम् -	डा.सि.आर् सन्तोष	260
श्रीहरिनामामृतपाणिनीयव्याकरणयोरुच्चस्थिप्रकरणस्य तुलनात्मकमध्ययनम्	डॉ. प्रीतिलक्ष्मी स्वाई	271
कुमारसम्भवस्य तिङन्तपदानि - मल्लिनाथीयविवेचनम् - विश्वबन्धु उपाध्यायः		278
योगवासिष्ठरामायणे शास्त्रव्याख्यानकौशलविमर्शः-	अमृता घोषः	282
उपनिषदि ब्रह्मस्वरूप-विमर्शः	अम्बरीष दासः	289
रसगङ्गाधरे नव्यन्यायभाषाशैली	डा. के. रतीष्	294
धातुवृत्तयः धातुकोशाश्च	डॉ. जयदेवदिण्डा	298
वाक्यपदीये वाक्यस्वरूपम्	ड० मलयपोडे	312
मनुसंहितालिखितायां समाजव्यवस्थायां नारीणां पदम् : दूषणं तत्प्रतिकारश्च		
	प्रशान्त कर्मकार्	320
वैयाकरणमतमनुसृत्य प्रतिभास्वरूपविचारः	डा० राजीवः पी. पी	329
ज्योतिर्गणितपद्धतीनां परिचयः	डा. हरिनारायणन्	334
अद्वैतनयेसत्तास्वरूपविमर्शः	डा. निषाद टि. एस्	339
भवभूतेकृतिषु सांख्ययोगमीमांसादर्शनतत्त्वानामन्वेषणम् -	डा० तानिया सिकदार	342
पाणिनीयव्याकरणे सूत्राणामेकवाक्यताविमर्शः -	डॉ. मनीषकुमारझाः	347
सर्वङ्कषाटीकायां व्याकरणालोचने मल्लिनाथस्य कतिपयाऽनवधानता - मृत्युञ्जयगराँड		354
परमपुरुषार्थसिद्धये भक्तिमार्गः	शुभाङ्कर बसकः	361
कातन्त्रव्याकरणसूत्रपरिचयः	डा० टि. वि गिरिजा	367
अष्टाध्याय्यां विभाषाधिकारेऽपि नित्यसमासविधानम्	पङ्कजराउलः	370
अलुक्समासविमर्शः	राजकुमार-मण्डलः	374
मधुसूदनसरस्वतीप्रणीते कृष्णकुतूहले भक्तिरसविमर्शः -	रिक्ता मण्डलः	380
जैनरीत्या बौद्धसम्मतप्रमाणलक्षणसमीक्षणम् -	श्रीशशांकशेखरपालः	388
जनकल्याणे नीतिशतकस्य माहात्म्यम्	समीरणः रायः	396
विभावना-विशेषक्तयोः समीक्षात्मकपर्यालोचनम्	शान्तनुः प्रधानः	401
संस्कृतव्याकरणदिशा ओडिआभाषायाः समीक्षणम् -	शिवानन्द बेहेरा	403
आचार्यधर्मकीर्तिकृतविविधसम्बन्धस्वरूपदूषणं तन्निराकरणञ्च -	सुजन-दासः	409
कादम्बरीहर्षचरितयोर्बाणभद्रस्य काव्यसौन्दर्यम्- प्रो. प्रसूनदत्तसिंहः, सुपर्णा सेनः		414
शिवसङ्कल्पः स्वरूपश्च पौराणिकग्रन्थेषु	डा. बिन्दुश्री के. एस्	419
न्यायसिद्धान्तमुक्तावल्यानुसारेण शब्दप्रमाणनिरूपणम् -	अश्वति एस्	422
वराहमिहिरस्य जीवचरितम् -	बि. नागराजः, डा. यादव	429
उपनिषद्ग्रन्थेषु पर्यावरणम्- एकमध्ययनम्	डा० गोविन्दसर्कार	432
रामायणमहाकाव्ये मोक्षस्य अवधारणा	तरणीकुमारपण्डा	437
अक्षपाददर्शनम्	डा. एस्. शिवकुमारः	445
सांख्ययोगौ पृथग्बालाः प्रवदन्ति न पण्डिताः	डा. अरविन्दमहापालः	451
Submission & Subscription		460

Knowledge of the Heart in *Ādi Śaṅkarācārya's Upaniṣad Commentary*

Jyothi. L¹

Abstract

Śri Śaṅkarācārya, a wise and intelligent man, interpreted ten Upaniṣads- Īśāvāsya Upaniṣad, Kena Upaniṣad, Kaṭha Upaniṣad, Praśna Upaniṣad, Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad, Māṇḍūkya Upaniṣad, Taittirīya Upaniṣad, Aitareya Upaniṣad, Chāndogya Upaniṣad and Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad, which are considered to be the most important and significant. His Upaniṣad writings and interpretations are legendary. Śaṅkara gives a lot of material information in this main Upaniṣads commentary. One of them is heart-centred wisdom. The circulatory system's pumping organ is the heart. The current review article covers Ādi Śaṅkarācārya's commentary on the idea of heart, including its etymology, meaning, anatomy, and position in the heart and venous drainage.

Key words

Hṛdayam- Śaṅkarācārya- Hita- Suṣumna

Introduction

Ādi Śaṅkarācārya was a profound philosopher, an enlightened soul, and possessed superhuman intelligence. Śaṅkarācārya's primary contributions were his remarkable exposition of Indian philosophical thought as well as his philosophy of Advaita Vedānta, which tends to place Hinduism in a unique position among religions. In support of his Advaitic views, he wrote extensive commentaries on the Brahmasūtra, the Upaniṣads, and the Bhagavad-Gīta. His works build on concepts from the Upaniṣads.

In the field of Indian philosophy, the Upaniṣads are a priceless source of knowledge. Śaṅkarācārya interpreted the ten Upaniṣads

1 Research Scholar, Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit Kalady Kerala.

(they are the Īśāvāsyā Upaniṣad, Kena Upaniṣad, Kaṭha Upaniṣad, Praśna Upaniṣad, Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad, Māṇḍūkya Upaniṣad, Taittirīya Upaniṣad, Aitareya Upaniṣad, Chāndogya Upaniṣad and Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad), which are thought to be the most important or noteworthy. The general misconception is that the Upaniṣads are only about spiritual knowledge. In fact, they are also about material knowledge. The Muṇḍakopaniṣad divides all knowledge into two categories: Parā Vidyā and Aparā Vidyā. Knowledge of man's true nature is known as Parā Vidyā, whereas knowledge of the material world is known as Aparā Vidyā (Muṇḍakopaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ. 1.1.4-5). We should use the second to direct our lives in order to arrive at the first. According to Vivekananda, both the Parā Vidyā and the Aparā Vidyā exist within the human mind, and everyone possesses the power and ability to combine secular and spiritual knowledge (the Parā Vidyā and the Aparā Vidyā) in order to achieve human excellence. (Complete works of Vivekananda 1.28, p.422)

As we turn the pages of Śāṅkarācārya's commentaries on the Principal Upaniṣads, we find numerous references to material knowledge. Heart knowledge is only one aspect of it. The Upaniṣad offers a unique perspective on the heart. In accordance with its psycho-somatic theory of the body-mind complex, it regards the heart as both the centre of blood circulation and the seat of consciousness. In the Upaniṣads, the word "Hṛdayaṁ" means heart. This article explains the knowledge of the heart mentioned in the commentaries on the Principal Upaniṣads by Śrī Śāṅkarācārya.

The human heart is located in the centre of the body. The heart's job is to keep healthy blood flowing through the body. In the Upaniṣads, the heart is referred to as "Hṛdayaṁ."

Etymology

Śāṅkarācārya divides the term Hṛdayaṁ into three parts in the Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad commentary: "Hṛ," "da," and "yaṁ." The letter "hṛ" is derived from the root word "hr̥ṇ harane." The word "hṛ" means "to take or to give." "Da," the second letter, stands for "charity." The word "yaṁ" comes from the root words "in gatau," which means "course" and "movement."

“तदेतत् हृदयमिति नाम ल्यैक्षरम्.... हृ इत्येकमक्षरं, अभिहरन्ति.... द इत्येतदप्येकमक्षरं एतदपि दानार्थस्य ददातेः द इत्येतद्रूपं हृदयनामाक्षरत्वेन निबद्धम्।.... तथा यमित्येतदप्येकमक्षरं इणो गत्यर्थस्य यमित्येतद्रूपम् ॥”

(Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 5.3.1.)

Definition

The word Hṛdayaṁ is defined as “Hṛdi ayaṁ” in the Chāndogya Upaniṣad commentary, which means that the seat of Ātman is in the heart. Except for this Upaniṣad, no other Upaniṣad contains a definition of “heart.” “हृदि अयमात्मा वर्तत इति यस्मात् तस्माद्भृदयं ...” (Chāndogyopaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 8.3.3.)

Location

Śāṅkara mentions the heart being on the left side of the kľoman and above the Yakṛt in the Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad commentary. (Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ. 1.1.1.)

Anatomy

The heart, according to Śri Śāṅkara, is a fleshy muscular organ that resembles a lotus bud.

“हृदयं नाम माम्सपिण्डं तस्मान्माम्सपिण्डात् पुण्डरीकाकारात्।” (Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ. 2.1.19.)

The lotus-like shape of the heart is stated in numerous Upaniṣads commentaries.

“पुण्डरीकाकारमाम्सपिण्डपरिच्छिन्नो हृदयाकाशो...” (Prašnopaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 3.6.)

“हृदयमिति पुण्डरीकाकारो माम्सपिण्डः” (Taittirīya Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ.1.6.2.)

The shape of the heart is revealed in the Taittirīya Upaniṣad commentary. According to Śāṅkara, the heart of a cow is discovered after it is slain (Taittirīya Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ.1.6.2). It is clear that Śāṅkarācārya understood the heart in this way. The size of a heart can vary depending on its age, size, and condition. The average clenched adult fist is the size of a normal, healthy adult heart. Śri Śāṅkara compares the heart to a lotus and the size of the heart having the length or size of a thumb in his Kāthopaniṣad commentary. “अंगुष्ठपरिमाणं हृदयपुण्डरीकम्” (Kāthopaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ .2.1.12)

Prāṇa Vāyu And Vyāna Vāyu In Heart

Prāṇa is centred in the heart. (Taittiriya Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 1.6.2). The heart's Vyāna Vāyu travels at a breakneck speed with the rest of the body. Vyāna pervades the entire body as rays from the sun, originating in the heart and radiating throughout the body, particularly in the joints, shoulders, and organ systems. (Prāśnopaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ.3.6.)

Śāṅkara says there are five holes in the heart in the Chāndogyopaniṣad commentary. The air that moves Prāṇa passes through the east hole, the north samāna, the south Vyāna, the west apāna, and the top of the Udāna. (Chāndogyopaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 3.13.1-5).

Venous Drainage of the Heart

The 'Hita' nerves come from the heart and are as delicate and subtle as the sun rays that reflect all over the place. These nerves are found throughout the body. The meal is absorbed via a complex network of sensitive and subtle nerves.

“हिता नाम हिता इत्येवं नाम्न्यो नाड्यः सिराः देहस्यान्नरसविपरिणामभूताः” (Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ .2.1.19)

“हिता नाम हिता इत्येवं ख्याताः नाड्यः ताश्चान्तर्हृदये मांसपिण्डे प्रतिष्ठिता भवन्ति।” (Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ .2.1.19)

The heart is like a grilled window because of the tangle of nerves and veins.

“यदेतन्तर्हृदये जालकमिव अनेकनाडीच्छिद्रबहुलत्वात् जालकमिव” (Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 4.2.3).

White, blue, brown, green, and red serums are loaded into the nerves Hita, which are as fine as a hair split into a thousand parts. The intermixture of nerve matter, bile, and phelgm in varied quantities results in a wide range of serum colours. The subtle body is packed with serums, white and other colours, and spread all over the body, with its seat in these nerves, which have the size of a thousandth part of a hair's tip. (Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 4.2.3).

The Śāṅkarācārya described the colour discrimination of nerves in the Chāndogyopaniṣad in scientific terms. “Āmāśaya” refers to the

upper region of the Nābhi and the area below the heart. Pittaṁ (bile) is the name for the fluid found there. When phlegm (kaphaṁ) is added to the fluid, it turns yellow. The nerve that is responsible for accepting the yellowish hue. The nerves turn blue when the “Pittarasaṁ” interacts with Vāta. The annarasaṁ and nerves take on a blue hue as a result of this. When there is a lot of phlegm, the Pittarasaṁ turns white, and when there is a lot of phlegm, the Pittarasaṁ turns a deep red hue due to the proximity of phlegm and iron. (Chāndogyopaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 8.6.1.) In the second chapter of Brhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad’s commentary, it is said that the body has 72000 “Hitas”. (Brhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 2.1.19.) Hathayoga and Ayurveda both verify this. (vikaspedia.in/health/ayush/nadi-vigyan,http://www.pijar.org/articles/Arch.vol.13 issue1/6.Rudragoudar%20Mrinal% 20Nandakumar.pdf)

According to the Kaṭhōpaniṣad (Kaṭhōpaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 2.3.16.) and Chāndogyopaniṣad (Chāndogyopaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 8.6.6.) commentary, a human heart contains roughly 101 nerves. The Suṣumna nerve is one of these nerves that separates from the top of the head and emerges. The Taittirīya Upaniṣad commentary explains how the nerves emerge in great detail. The Suṣumna nerves originate in the heart, travel to the palate, where there is a growth of flesh similar to the breast, divide the hair and the brain in half, and emerge. (Taittirīya Upaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 1.6.2.) According to Śri Śāṅkara’s commentary on the Praśnopaniṣad. (Praśnopaniṣad Śāṅkarabhāṣyaṁ 3.6) 101 important nerves originated, with one nerve branching into 100 nerves and each of the branching nerves developed around 70000 subbranches. The total number of main nerves, branching nerves, and sub-branched nerves in a human body is 72 core, 72 lakh, and 10201 nerves (727210201).

Conclusion

Advaita Vedānta philosophy, a non-dualistic theory based on the Upaniṣads, was developed and codified by Ādi Śāṅkara. He published commentary on the Prasthānatrayi- Upaniṣads, Brahmasūtra, and Bhagavad Gīta that were considered authoritative. Many people

believe that the commentary on the Upaniṣads is limited to the study of Ātman, however it references a lot of material science. The knowledge of the Heart is only a part of it. Despite his reputation as a spiritualist, these newly uncovered facts demonstrate his strong understanding of the materialistic side of existence. The fact that Śri Śaṅkara commented on the Upaniṣads, notably the Knowledge of the Heart, without any instruments or tools is amazing. This demonstrates the great Ācharya's high level of intelligence and wisdom. The Upaniṣad intellectuals only discuss the intellectual aspects of it, never delving into the physical science contained in it. The Upaniṣad would have been more acceptable to the average man if they had done so. It will also aid the research schools on this subject.

Works Cited

- Gambhirananda, Swami. Eight Upanishads with the commentary of Sri Sankaracharya Vol.1, Advaita Ashrama, Kolkata,1957
- Jha, Ganganath. Chandogya Upanishad with Shankara Bhashya, Oriental Book Agency, Poona,1942
- Madhavananda, Swami. Brihadaranyaka Upanishad Shankara Bhashya , Advaitaashrama, Almora,1950.
- Ten Principal Upaniṣads with Śaṅkarabhāṣya in original Sanskrit Vol.1, Motilal Banarsidas, Delhi, 1964.
- Vivekananda, Swami. Complete Works of Swami Vivekananda.Vol.1, Advaita Asrama, Kolkata, 1945.

KIRANĀVALĪ
Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation
The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XIV.
Book III-IV
JULY – DECEMBER 2022

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram-36
Sanskritresearchfoundation@gmail.com